

Theoretical determination of the ionization potential of cysteinamide

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Manuscript received 4 July 2006, accepted 16 October 2006

Abstract : Adiabatic and vertical ionization potentials (IPs) of cysteinamide in the gas phase and in solutions have been calculated with the density functional theory (B3LYP, B3P86) and *ab initio* HF methods using the 6-31+G* basis set, respectively. Six possible conformers of cysteinamide and its charged states have been optimized employing B3LYP/6-31+G* level. All the ionization potentials of the six cysteinamide conformers in our work are positive values no matter whether in the gas phase or in solutions, and decrease with increasing of dielectric constants in solutions. The spin density (ρ) on cationic states of cysteinamide conformers is mainly located on S3, N6 and O10 atoms. The positive charge is mostly distributed around the C7, S3 atoms and all hydrogen atoms.

Keywords : Ionization potential, cysteinamide.

It is well known that the amino acids and peptides form the building blocks of proteins. However, in peptides and proteins small amino acid molecules are connected with amino acid amide bonds and both the terminal amino acids and cysteinamide have a free NH₂ group. The amino amides are the most stable derivatives of amino acids. This stability is partly due to the strong resonance interaction between the nonbonding electrons on nitrogen and the carbonyl group. The amide nitrogen is no longer a strong base, and the C-N bond has restricted rotation because of its partial double-bond character. We can use the resonance forms to explain the partial double-bond character and restricted resonance of an amide bond. In a peptide, this partial double-bond character results in six atoms being held rather rigidly in a plane. It is important to study the structures and properties of small amide molecules and amide bonds. IPs are very important properties for atoms and molecules, as they are fundamental in assessing the electron donating ability. Many theoretical and experimental investigation have been carried out to study the ionization potential of atoms and molecules¹. Recent developments of experimental techniques for the study of ion-molecule reactions and structure-reactivity relationships made it possible to determine accurate ionization potentials for a wide variety of organic molecules. Cysteinamide (CH₂SHCHNH₂CONH₂) is an amide derivative of cysteine and differs from serinamide because it contains a sulfur atom. The ionization potentials of

cysteinamide have not yet been determined by theoretical and experimental methods. The calculated ionization potentials of cysteinamide should present some comparable results for other theorists and should be helpful to the experimentalists who specialize in this area.

Here, six conformations have been found on the global potential energy surface of cysteinamide at the B3LYP/6-31+G* level (see Fig. 1). IPs of cysteinamide have been calculated with the density functional theory (B3LYP, B3P86) and *ab initio* HF methods using 6-31+G* basis set, respectively.

Computational details :

The conformers of cysteinamide neutral states and their corresponding cationic states are fully optimized employing density functional theory (B3LYP, B3P86) and *ab initio* HF methods with 6-31+G* basis set, respectively. Frequency calculations are performed at the same level of theory to ensure that the systems represent true minima on the potential energy surface and to provide corrections for the zero-point vibrational effects. As a result, six stable neutral states and six stable cationic states have been found.

The chemical processes of molecule M removing an electron can be expressed as follows :

The calculation formulas defined according to the energy

Fig. 1. Six conformers of cysteinamide obtained at the B3LYP/6-31+G* level.

differences are as follows :

- (1) $AIP = E^+ (\text{opt}) - E^0 (\text{opt})$
- (2) $VIP = E^+ (\text{Geo} = 0) - E^0 (\text{opt})$
- (3) Reorganization energy (RE^+) is the energy difference between the cationic state in the geometry of its neutral state and the optimized cationic state, which can be used to evaluate the structural changes for the cationic state in the geometry of neutral state upon nuclear relaxation,

$$RE^+ = E^+ (\text{Geo} = 0) - E^+ (\text{opt}) = VIP - AIP$$

where AIP refers to adiabatic ionization potential, VIP refers to vertical ionization potential, $E^0 (\text{opt})$ refers to the energy of optimized neutral species, $E^+ (\text{Geo} = 0)$ refers to the energy of cation in the optimized neutral geometry.

To describe the effects of the surrounding medium, the polarized continuum model (PCM) was used to perform calculations on the optimized gas phase structures². These calculations are performed employing a series of

solutions, such as chloroform, acetone, nitromethane and water (the dielectric constants $\epsilon = 4.9, 20.7, 38.2$ and 78.39 , respectively).

All of the computations were carried out using the Gaussian98 program package.

Results and discussion

For simplicity, 1C denotes the optimized neutral conformer of cysteinamide, and $1C^+$ denotes the optimized corresponding cationic structure. Similarly, the same applies to other conformers.

The relative energies of the six cysteinamide conformers calculated employing density functional theory B3LYP method with 6-31+G* basis set in the gas phase have been given in Table S1 in supplemental information. The IPs calculated using density functional theory (DFT) and *ab initio* methods in the gas phase have been listed in Table 1. The ionization potentials performed using PCM model have been summarized in Table 2. In supplemental information, the significant structural parameters of 1C, $1C^+$ and 2C, $2C^+$ have been displayed in Table S2, and those of 3C, $3C^+$ and 4C, $4C^+$ have been displayed in Table S3, and those of 5C, $5C^+$ and 6C, $6C^+$ have

Table 1. Calculated ionization potential (IP) in the gas phase using density functional theory (DFT) B3LYP, B3P86 and *ab initio* HF methods at 6-31+G* basis set^a

Methods	Species	AIP	VIP
B3LYP	1C	8.34 (8.31) ^b	8.63
	2C	7.89 (7.92)	8.83
	3C	8.33 (8.30)	8.82
	4C	8.26 (8.22)	8.62
	5C	8.04 (8.05)	8.80
	6C	8.33 (8.28)	8.80
B3P86	1C	8.90 (8.87)	9.21
	2C	8.39 (8.42)	9.40
	3C	8.88 (8.85)	9.40
	4C	8.80 (8.77)	9.18
	5C	8.56 (8.57)	9.38
	6C	8.88 (8.83)	9.38
HF	1C	8.22 (8.20)	8.68
	2C	8.13 (8.10)	8.64
	3C	7.93 (7.91)	8.37
	4C	7.78 (7.78)	8.47
	5C	7.95 (7.93)	8.41
	6C	7.78 (7.77)	8.34

^aAll of the units are in eV. ^bThe values in parentheses refer to the ionization potentials with zero-point energy correction.

Table 2. Calculated adiabatic and vertical ionization potentials and reorganization energies (RE^+) using the PCM model at B3LYP/6-31+G* level

	ϵ^a	AIP (VIP)	RE^{+b}
1C	1.0	8.34 (8.63)	0.29
	4.9	6.77 (7.12)	0.35
	20.7	6.43 (6.81)	0.38
	38.2	6.38 (6.76)	0.38
	78.39	6.08 (6.48)	0.40
2C	1.0	7.89 (8.83)	0.94
	4.9	6.36 (7.26)	0.90
	20.7	6.07 (6.94)	0.87
	38.2	6.02 (6.89)	0.87
	78.39	5.82 (6.55)	0.73
3C	1.0	8.33 (8.82)	0.49
	4.9	6.75 (7.28)	0.53
	20.7	6.41 (6.96)	0.55
	38.2	6.36 (6.92)	0.56
	78.39	6.07 (6.60)	0.53
4C	1.0	8.26 (8.62)	0.36
	4.9	6.67 (7.02)	0.35
	20.7	6.34 (6.68)	0.34
	38.2	6.29 (6.64)	0.34
	78.39	5.98 (6.30)	0.32
5C	1.0	8.04 (8.80)	0.76
	4.9	6.49 (7.25)	0.76
	20.7	6.19 (6.93)	0.75
	38.2	6.14 (6.89)	0.75
	78.39	5.91 (6.57)	0.66
6C	1.0	8.33 (8.80)	0.48
	4.9	6.72 (7.27)	0.54
	20.7	6.38 (6.95)	0.57
	38.2	6.33 (6.90)	0.58
	78.39	6.01 (6.59)	0.58

^a All of the units are in eV and $\epsilon = 1.0$ refers to the results in the gas phase. ^b RE^+ refers to the result in the ionization process.

been depicted in Table S4, respectively. All atomic net charges of six neutral and six cationic states of cysteinamide conformers and all atomic spin densities of six cationic states calculated employing B3LYP/6-31+G* level are shown in Tables S5, S6 and S7 in supplemental information, respectively. The six conformers of neutral cysteinamide optimized at B3LYP/6-31+G* level have been displayed in Fig. 1. The relative energy plot of the six neutral conformers at B3LYP/6-31+G* level is drawn in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Relative energies of six conformers of cysteinamide at B3LYP/6-31+G* level in the gas phase.

Ionization potential :

From Fig. 2, we can see that the relative energy order of the six conformers is $4C > 6C > 2C > 1C > 3C > 5C$ at B3LYP/6-31+G* level. From Table 1, we can see that the relative order of adiabatic ionization potentials of the six conformers is $1C > 3C \approx 6C > 4C > 5C > 2C$ for B3LYP and B3P86 methods, and $1C > 2C > 5C > 3C > 4C \approx 6C$ for HF method. Vertical ionization potentials of the six conformers are $2C \approx 3C > 5C \approx 6C > 1C > 4C$ for B3LYP and B3P86 methods, and $1C > 2C > 4C > 5C > 3C > 6C$ for HF method. The zero-point vibrational energy corrections have been performed for adiabatic ionization potentials. From Table 1, we can see that the corrections are very small for cysteinamide conformers.

From Table 2 we can see that the adiabatic and vertical ionization potentials of the six cysteinamide conformers decrease with increasing of the dielectric constants in solutions. And these values in solutions are smaller than the results in the gas phase. This indicates that cysteinamides are easier to oxidize in solutions than in the gas phase.

The conformer changes have been accompanied by the ionization of neutral cysteinamide, and six stable cations have been found. The changes of bond lengths and dihedral angles can be seen from Table S2, Table S3 and Table S4 in supplemental information. On the whole, the lengths of $R(C1-C2)$ and $R(C2-C7)$ of six cationic states $1C^+$, $2C^+$, $3C^+$, $4C^+$, $5C^+$ and $6C^+$ increase when compared with the neutral states. The lengths of $R(C1-S3)$, $R(C2-N6)$ and $R(C7-N11)$ decrease. However, the lengths of $R(C7-O10)$ of $1C^+$, $3C^+$, $4C^+$ and $6C^+$ decrease by $0.009 \sim 0.014 \text{ \AA}$ and increase by 0.021 \AA and

0.022 Å for 2C⁺ and 5C⁺, respectively. Part of the reason likely owes to the intramolecular hydrogen bonds. However, the changes of the bond lengths are different for different conformers. On the whole, the changes of bond lengths R(C2-N6) and R(C2-C7) are larger. All of the main molecular skeletons have been distorted significantly. For example, the dihedral angles D (N6, C2, C7, N11) of 1C⁺, 2C⁺, 3C⁺, 4C⁺, 5C⁺ and 6C⁺ have changed greatly, and the variations are 35°, 117.2°, 172°, 23.4°, 2.2° and 26.3°, respectively. However, the planarity of the peptide bond C7-N11 is still kept as those of the neutral states, that is to say that it cannot be affected significantly for cysteinamide upon ionization. The dihedral angles D (C2, C7, N11, H14), D (C2, C7, N11, H15), D (O10, C7, N11, H14) and D (O10, C7, N11, H15) of neutral state 1C are -177°, 4.2°, 0.73° and -177°, respectively and this proved the planarity of the peptide bond C7-N11 of 1C. The corresponding values of cationic state 1C⁺ are 178.6°, -1.0°, -0.7° and 179.7°, and this indicates the planarity of the peptide bond C7-N11 of cationic states 1C⁺. Similarly, the same holds for other conformers. On the other hand, the change of hydrogen bonds indicates the changes of the conformers for cysteinamide upon ionization. Here, the hydrogen bonds refer to the shortest hydrogen bonds that we found in the neutral states and cationic states. And these shortest hydrogen bonds are depicted in Fig. 1 by dashed lines. For conformer 1C, the intramolecular N6-H9 hydrogen bond (2.538 Å) and the O10...H13 hydrogen bond (2.417 Å) disappear, and the intramolecular N11...H8 (2.558 Å) and O10...H14 (2.567 Å) hydrogen bonds appear. For conformer 2C, the intramolecular O10...H13 hydrogen bond (2.487 Å) and the N11...H8 hydrogen bond (2.548 Å) disappear, and the intramolecular N6-H15 (2.262 Å) and O10...H14 (2.549 Å) hydrogen bonds appear. For conformer 3C, the intramolecular O10...H4 hydrogen bond (2.522 Å) decrease by 0.391 Å, and N6...H15 hydrogen bond (2.211 Å) disappear and N6...H5 (2.347 Å) appear. For conformer 4C, the intramolecular N6...H15 hydrogen bond (2.496 Å) decrease by 0.076 Å, and O10...H14 hydrogen bond (2.506 Å) disappear and O10...H4 (2.561 Å) appear. For conformer 5C, the intramolecular N6...H15 hydrogen bond (2.220 Å) increase by 0.033 Å, and the O10...H14 hydrogen bond (2.541 Å) increase by 0.22 Å. For conformer 6C, the intramolecular N6...H15 hydrogen bond (2.256 Å) increased by 0.148 Å, and O10...H14 hydrogen bond (2.531 Å) disappear and O10...H5 (2.310 Å) appear. These changes of hydrogen bonds are the result from detachment of an electron from the neutral states of cysteinamide.

And the structural changes for the cationic states in the geometry of neutral state upon nuclear relaxation have been produced, which can be proved by the reorganization energies RE⁺ in Table 2.

Atomic net charges and spin densities :

Spin densities have proved particularly useful. Many compounds can be induced to form cations by the gain of an electron. The resulting ions are of course radical ions and they give rise to an electron spin resonance spectrum. Subtle changes in the geometry of the molecules and the strength of any hydrogen bonding can be expected to occur on oxidation. Such small changes in bond lengths and bond angles may play a crucial role in facilitating rapid electron transfer. In order to fully interpret observable changes occurring on oxidation, accurate quantum chemical-base predictions for model compounds are needed. Atomic net charges and spin densities calculated employing B3LYP/6-31+G* level are shown in Tables S5, S6 and S7 in supplemental information, respectively. The spin density (ρ) on cationic states of cysteinamide conformers is mainly located on S3, N6 and O10 atoms. There are also differences in the charge distributions. The positive charge is mostly distributed around the C7, S3 atoms and all hydrogen atoms. Even though the cations are further oxidation, C1, C2, N6, N11 and O10 atoms remain to be negatively charges.

Conclusions :

In our work, the ionization potentials of six cysteinamide conformers have been calculated using DFT (B3LYP and B3P86) and *ab initio* HF methods with 6-31+G* basis set, respectively. The relative energy orders of the six conformers are 4C > 6C > 2C > 1C > 3C > 5C at B3LYP/6-31+G* level. The relative orders of adiabatic ionization potentials of the six conformers are 1C > 3C ≈ 6C > 4C > 5C > 2C for B3LYP and B3P86 methods, and 1C > 2C > 5C > 3C > 4C ≈ 6C for HF method. Vertical ionization potentials of the six conformers are 2C ≈ 3C > 5C ≈ 6C > 1C > 4C for B3LYP and B3P86 methods, and 1C > 2C > 4C > 5C > 3C > 6C for HF method. Furthermore, these ionization potentials decrease with increase of dielectric constants in solutions. The conformer changes have been accompanied by the ionization of neutral cysteinamide and six stable cations have been found. And the conformer changes have been analyzed according to the bond lengths, dihedral angles and intramolecular hydrogen bonds. The spin density (ρ) on cationic states of cysteinamide conformers is mainly located on S3, N6 and O10 atoms. The positive charge is mostly distributed

around the C7, S3 atoms and all hydrogen atoms. Even though the cations are further oxidation, C1, C2, N6, N11 and O10 atoms remain to be negatively charges.

Acknowledgement

This work is supported by the Natural Science Foundation of Shandong Province (Z2002F01), the State Key Laboratory Foundation of Crystal Material, and the National Natural Science Foundation of China (29673025).

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